

Stock Pricing And Stock Market Determinants in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the extent to which stock pricing is influenced by stock market determinants, with particular reference to macroeconomic determinants of stock pricing, using market capitalization as a proxy for stock pricing and interest rate; exchange rate and nominal GDP as macroeconomic variables for the period 1981–2022, in Nigeria. Data for the variables were obtained from the CBN statistical bulletin 2022 edition. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimation technique in a multiple regression model was used to estimate the relationship between stock pricing and stock market determinants. The findings showed that stock pricing is significantly determined by the interest rate and nominal GDP. Based on this, the study recommended that policymakers should focus on maintaining macroeconomic stability, fostering a conducive investment climate, and improving market regulations to mitigate volatility and enhance market efficiency.

Keywords: *stock pricing, stock market, micro and macro factors.*

1.0 Introduction

Stock markets have been identified as locations for engaging in economic transactions such as buying and selling stocks or shares, which are the ownership claims of businesses (Rjumohan, 2019). Stock markets are also known as share markets and equity markets. A stock exchange, also called a securities exchange or bourse, is the name given to the facility for engaging in the buying and selling of shares, stocks, bonds, or other financial instruments.

The stock market is an essential element of the capital market, where investment capital is raised. Investment capital, as an important factor in society, can enrich society's wealth when effectively and efficiently used (Nguyen and Pham, 2021). Thus, the stock market can be viewed as a medium to encourage savings, help channel savings

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into productive investments, and improve the efficiency and productivity of investments (Alam et al. 2016). Consequently, the growth of the stock market should not be undertaken solely for domestic resource mobilisation but should also be strengthened by the need to attract foreign capital in non-debt-creating forms (Rjumohan, 2019).

Stock markets in the form we know today did not appear until the 1500s. Instead, there were markets exchanging government securities, debt instruments, and commodities, which were mainly confined to Western Europe from a time as far back as the 11th century, under the shade of trees and in coffee houses.

The Nigerian stock market has emerged as a significant arena for investment and economic growth. Understanding the determinants of stock pricing within this dynamic market is imperative for investors, policymakers, and financial analysts. Stock markets are, without any doubt, an integral and indispensable part of a country's economy; but the impact of stock markets on a country's economy can be different from how other countries' stock markets affect their economies. This is because the impact of stock markets on the economy depends on various factors, like the organisation of stock exchanges, its relationship with other components of the financial system, the system of governance in the country, and so on. All of these factors are distinct for each country; therefore, the impact of stock markets on a country's economy is also distinct.

The study of factors affecting stock prices is often a matter of debate. The market price of the share is a very important factor that influences investors' decision-making (Pongsuppat and Pongsuppat, 2019). The market price, or economic price, of a product or service is the amount for which a good or service is offered in the market. It is simply the amount at which goods and services are sold or exchanged in the market (Fadiran and Olowoekere, 2016). Furthermore, price could be seen as a financial expression of the worth of the product (the more reasons why setting the right price is important). Share price is thus the price of any share in the stock market and the cost of purchasing the share. Share price can also be seen as a measure of the value content of cash flows (Almashaqbeh et al. 2018).

Different views by different professionals have been held as far as the pricing of an asset is concerned. In an efficient market, stock prices could be internally or externally determined. Internal factors determining share prices are those factors that emanate from within the organisation and lie within its control. Such factors include earnings per share, dividend policy, payout ratio, retention ratio, size of the firm, return

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on equity, and management (Mehr-un-Nisa & Nishat, 2012; Nguyen & Pham, 2022). External factors, on the other hand, are factors that are outside the control of management and include such things as gross domestic product, inflation rate, interest rate, exchange rate, or political stability, among others (Sindhu et al., 2014; Alam et al., 2016).

Like determinants of demand and supply for every other commodity, demand for and supply of shares, according to Fadiran and Olowookere (2016), can be determined by advertising and sales promotion, training and organisation of the sales force, effectiveness of distribution, and quality of after-sales service. As a result, these factors are within the company's control. Consequently, such factors as the price of substitutes, the price of complements, consumers' disposable income, and consumer tastes and fashions are part of the factors that are outside the control of the business.

From the foregoing, it can be asserted that all the determinants of demand and supply interact to determine the price of shares. Furthermore, combining all the factors enumerated above, it can be submitted that factors affecting the price of equity can be viewed from macro and microeconomic perspectives. Macroeconomic factors include general economic conditions, i.e., how the economy is performing, government regulations such as new government policies, inflation, money supply, industry competition, uncontrollable natural or environmental factors, and industrial actions, among others. Consequently, the microeconomic factors or organisation-specific factors are board changes, management changes, new asset creation, dividends, and good financial performance, among others. In this regard, we summarised factors that are likely to determine the price of shares to include: real GDP, interest rate, inflation rate, exchange rate, money supply, and firm measures of performance such as earnings per share, dividend per share, net assets per share, return on equity, return on assets, and gearing ratio, among others.

Given the plethora of factors affecting stock pricing, Oseni (nd) noted that factors affecting asset prices are numerous and inexhaustible and can be categorised into firm, industry, country, international, market, and non-market factors, as well as economic and non-economic factors. All the factors can be summarised into two classes: micro and macro factors. Irrespective of the classification, factors in each class of the classification are inexhaustible.

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In addition to the aforementioned factors, information plays a key role in shaping investors' attitudes towards the price they pay for shares and the price at which they are willing to sell their shares. This assertion is predicated on the fact that stock prices will quickly adjust when new information emerges and is absorbed by investors. Consequently, it is assumed that an efficient market is an exchange market where the securities traded reflect all information that occurs quickly and accurately. However, it has been established in some studies that, while both company-specific news and the general economy may influence trading behaviour, using news-induced investor expectations alone as a trading strategy is inadequate. This is because, in some cases, investors tend to buy after positive news, which generates buying pressure and pushes prices higher, and sell after negative news that results in a price drop.

Furthermore, classical economic concepts postulate that market prices are primarily determined by the interaction of the forces of supply and demand. According to Machmuddah, Suhartono, and Sumaryati (2020), demand theory explains that there is a relationship between stock prices and the number of requests for shares, so that it can be explained that the increase in share prices arises because of the number of requests. If there is a decrease in the price of shares, the demand for shares will also decrease. This condition is used as an illustration for investors to obtain information available on the stock market and use it as a reference for investors to invest their capital, so that investors will react and new stock prices will be created.

The current study is an attempt to investigate the extent to which stock pricing can be influenced by both micro and macro factors. However, due to the paucity of data and the fact that the present study is not limited to the stock pricing of a single firm, the focus of this study is therefore to investigate the determinants of stock pricing from the perspective of external or macroeconomic factors.

2.0 Literature review

Conceptually, stock pricing in Nigeria is influenced by a multitude of factors. These factors are of importance to investors as they will enable them to make informed decisions before investing in any particular firm. While considering factors that may impact stock price changes, different authors have attributed different factors to share price changes. Enow and Brijal (2016), Pongsuppat & Pongsuppat (2019), and Nguyen & Pham (2022) attributed changes in stock prices to book value per share, earnings per

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share, dividend, gross domestic product and net asset value, dividend policy, payout ratio, retention ratio, size of the firm, return on equity, and management. Conversely, other authors (Adebisi & Lawal, 2015; Rjoub, Civcir & Resatoglu, 2017) have also revealed that share prices are solely determined by factors such as interest rates, political events, lawsuits, mergers and acquisitions, government policies, investor sentiments and availability of substitutes, analyst reports, and technical influences. Stock prices could also be affected by the movement of macroeconomic variables such as gross domestic product, inflation rate, interest rate, exchange rate, or political stability (Maku & Atanda, 2010). From the foregoing, it can be concluded that there hasn't been an acceptable explanation of the determinants of share price in different countries of the world.

Theoretical Issues

Theoretical frameworks provide lenses through which we understand the complexities of stock pricing. The theoretical bases for this study are the efficient market hypothesis (EMH), random walk theory, behavioural finance theory, and the rational expectations hypothesis.

Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH)

This theory shows that a significant number of profit-oriented investors respond to changes in business formation. Each of the stock investors evaluates the market value of the stock prices when new formations are made in the company. According to Singh (2018), one of the most significant theories is the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), which is based on the assumption that rational investors in the market react to the available information, such as company fundamentals and other important declarations about the company, to decide whether to buy or sell stock. If they feel that the information is positive, then they retain the shares they have already bought or buy the ones that were not purchased earlier, and vice versa. Investors buying and selling stocks are responsible for changes in the stock price. According to Cleary (2017), at any given time, the stock prices show unbiased representations of available information and forecast the value of the stock. The efficient market hypothesis (EMH) posits that stock prices reflect all available information, implying that prices instantly adjust to new information. However, in emerging markets like Nigeria, deviations from EMH due to

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inefficiencies, information asymmetry, and behavioural biases warrant exploration. Factors such as corporate earnings, macroeconomic indicators, investor sentiments, and global market trends play pivotal roles in conceptualising stock pricing dynamics in Nigeria.

Random walk theory

This theory states that stock prices are random and cannot be predicted by any means. This theory indicates that the market prices of stocks evolve and that new information about stock prices is distributed over a period of time. The stock price changes randomly and has no connection to the previous price at a given time. This theory explains that if the stock prices are in a random pattern, the market can be considered efficient as all knowledge available is discounted. This theory has been extensively accepted and verified in capital markets all over the world (Dockery, Vergari, and Vergari, 2001). Different researchers have disproved this hypothesis of patterns in stock prices; others have supported the theory. For investors to have an optimal investment in the stock market, 'value investing strategy' must be acknowledged. Many investors considered this strategy, particularly after the global financial crisis of 2007, when they analysed the low-priced earning stocks and low-priced book-to-book stocks that are likely to outperform stock growth.

Behavioural finance theory

This theory states that investors do not behave rationally; rather, they invest based on psychological and behavioural factors; for example, they will invest in the stock if the stock price is increasing, even if there are no significant changes in the company's fundamentals. The theory suggests that psychological and behavioural nuances must be considered before investing in the stock market, as they can result in extreme stock fluctuations. Regarding this theory, Morck et al. (1990) assert that there seem to be good theoretical as well as empirical reasons to believe that investor sentiment, also referred to as fads and fashions, affects stock prices. By investor sentiments, we mean beliefs held by some investors that cannot be rationally justified. Such investors are sometimes referred to as noise traders. To affect prices, these less-than-rational beliefs have to be correlated across noise traders; otherwise, trades based on mistaken judgements would cancel out. When investor sentiment affects the demand of enough investors, security

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prices diverge from fundamental values. Additionally, behavioural finance theories elucidate how psychological biases and investor sentiments influence stock pricing mechanisms, especially in the context of Nigeria's market.

Rational Expectations Hypothesis

This hypothesis highlights the individual behaviours of various people based on information about the stock market at a given time. Individuals make decisions based on what the outcome of the stock market price will be before investing, largely to avoid capital losses. Previous mistakes made in investment can be avoided by using available information to predict future market values (Cherry, 2017).

Summarily, the first theory says that, in making investment decisions, managers rely on the stock market as a source of information, which may or may not be correct about future fundamentals. The second statement says that the stock market is a passive predictor of future activity that managers do not rely on to make investment decisions. The third theory says that the stock market exerts pressure on investment quite aside from its informational and financing role, because managers have to cater to investors' opinions in order to protect their livelihood. Finally, the fourth theory, which is perhaps the most common view of the stock market's influence, says that the stock market affects investment through its influence on the cost of funds and external financing.

Empirical Issues

In the Nigerian context, empirical investigations reveal the practical manifestations of stock pricing determinants. Studies reveal a confluence of factors impacting stock prices, including interest rates, inflation, exchange rates, corporate governance practices, and political stability. Empirical evidence showcases the significance of these variables in explaining stock price movements and volatility, providing insights for investors and policymakers. A review of some of these literatures would suffice.

Gunu and Idris (2009) examined macroeconomic variables that are responsible for share price fluctuations in Nigeria. Secondary data on Nigerian stock market share prices covering the period 1980–2006 was used. Multiple regression was used to analyse the data. The results showed that inflation, money supply, total deficit index of industrial production, interest rate, and GDP all have a significant influence on stock prices. It was recommended that in order to monitor and control stock prices in Nigeria

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through macroeconomic variables, emphasis should be given to money supply, GDP, and total deficits.

Mehr -un -Nisa and Nishat (2012) empirically examined the relationship between stock prices, financial fundamentals, and macroeconomic factors on the Karachi Stock Exchange using the dynamic panel Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) technique on the data of 221 firms during 1995–2006. The analysis attempted to obtain efficient parameter estimates and to check the consistency of the link between stock price behaviour, company fundamentals, and macroeconomic factors. It was found that previous behaviour of stock prices, company size, and previous earnings per share are the most important factors. Furthermore, macroeconomic indicators such as GDP growth, interest rate, and financial depth have a significant relationship with stock prices. The study recommended that, while making decisions, investors should consider company information as well as the country's macroeconomic situation simultaneously.

Adebisi and Lawal (2015) reviewed the factors that determine firms' equity share prices, with a special focus on the microeconomic factors. Dividend per share, earning per share, book value per share, dividend payout, price earnings ratio, and size of the firm were identified as significant factors impacting the firm's equity share price by the corporate finance scholars.

Sharif, Purohit, and Pillai (2015) identified the main determinants affecting share prices in the Bahrain financial market. The study analysed a panel data set of 41 companies listed on the Bahrain stock exchange for the period 2006–2010. Eight firm-specific variables, namely return on equity, book value per share, earnings per share, dividend per share, dividend yield, price earnings, debt to assets, and firm size, were used to infer their impact on the market price of shares in the respective market. The estimation method was based on pooled OLS regression with robust standard errors, fixed effects, and random effects models. The results indicated that the variables return on equity, book value per share, dividend per share, dividend yield, price earnings, and firm size are significant determinants of share prices in the Bahrain market. The implications of these findings are that investors can make optimum investment decisions and be assured of fair returns if they consider these determinants, which have evolved to be significant contributors to the market price of shares in Bahrain.

Alam, Mihar, and Karim (2016) investigated the main forces that affect share prices in the capital market of Bangladesh using a panel data set of seven cement

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companies listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) for the period 2006–2015. An investigation approach designed with ordinary least squares (OLS) regression with fixed effects and random effects models was used for the study. Six fundamental and technical issues, namely Earning Per Share (EPS), Net Asset Value Per Share (NAVPS), Price Earnings (P/E), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Consumer Price Index (CPI), and Interest Rate Spread (IRS), were brought to light as the major determinants of prices in the cement industry. The findings claimed that these variables are instrumental in affecting the share prices in the Bangladesh market as far as the cement industry is concerned. Among these factors, EPS, NAVPS, P/E, and CPI have been found to be significantly instrumental for the cement industry in Bangladeshi contexts, while other variables were not found to be noticeably significant. Hence, the study recommends that present and potential investors consider these factors prior to trading and injecting funds into securities, as the study witnessed volatility in share prices due to the fluctuations of these factors.

Enow and Brijlal (2016) investigated the determinants of share prices using fourteen companies listed on the Johannesburg stock exchange from 2009 to 2013. Using a multiple regression analysis, the result revealed that dividend per share, earnings per share, and price-earnings ratio account for 57.8% of share price movements. Furthermore, earnings per share and price earnings were significantly positively correlated to share prices, although dividends per share were not. The findings implied that managers can create value for their shareholders by increasing dividends per share, earnings per share, and price earnings.

Fadiran and Olowookere (2016) empirically utilised both accounting and macroeconomic variables to assess the determinants of share price (SP) and their relative importance on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). The Dividend Share Valuation Model, where SP is the discounted value of a stream of dividends conditional on information, was adopted. Seventy-two dividend-paying firms listed on the NSE between 2000 and 2011 were sampled. Generalised least squares and stepwise regression estimation techniques were used to evaluate the panel model at 5% level of statistical significance. The results of both techniques revealed that firm performance and macroeconomic conditions are major determinants of share prices on the NSE.

Rjoub et al. (2017) investigated the relationship between Turkish bank stock prices and a set of micro and macro variables. The study employed a fixed panel data

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analysis and a Dumitrescu and Hurlin panel Granger causality test for the period from the 3rd quarter of 1995 to the 4th quarter of 2015. In general, both macro and micro variables were found to reliably price the bank stocks. Specifically, the findings showed that asset quality, management quality, earning, size, money supply, and interest rate are significantly related to stock price. Also, bidirectional causality was found between bank size, asset quality, money supply, and bank stock price. It was suggested that investors should pay attention to bank-specific information in their decisions. Moreover, the result indicated that bank stock prices react negatively to economic crises.

Pongsuppat and Pongsuppat (2019) determined the factors that cause stock prices to increase or decrease. Eight explanatory variables, including dividend yield, growth, leverage, return on equity, book value per share, earnings per share, price-earning (P/E) ratio, and net profit after tax, have been selected, while one controllable variable was set as firm-size. Completed financial data of 577 samples from companies listed on the Thailand Stock Exchange (TSE) SET 100 Index, excluding the financing and banking sector, during the period of 2009–2018 was analyzed. A multiple regression model with statistical testing at the significant level of 0.05 was implemented. The results indicated a strong positive and significant association between return on equity, earnings per share, price earnings, and net profit after tax on the firms' stock price. In contrast, dividend yield was the only factor that had a negative relationship with stock price.

Machmuddah et al. (2020) examined the factors that influence stock prices using manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesian stock exchange in the period 2017–2019 as research samples. Factors selected for the study included interest rates, exchange rates, and the company's financial performance proxied by return on assets (ROA), debt-to-equity ratio (DER), earnings per share (EPS), price-earnings ratio (PER), and dividends per share (DPS). Multiple regression was used as a tool for data analysis. The results showed that the company's financial performance factors, proxied by EPS and PER, affect stock prices. However, interest rates, exchange rates, and company financial performance factors proxied by ROA, DER, and DPS have no effect on stock prices. The implication of the research was that it is important for investors to be careful when making investment decisions because many factors affect stock prices; therefore, it is necessary to analyse before making investment decisions.

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Abdallah et al. (2022) investigated the financial determinants of the market stock price in Jordan using empirical evidence from the industrial companies listed on the Amman Stock Exchange for 2010–2018, with a panel data analysis of 57 industrial companies. The study sample consisted of all the companies in the population, for a total of 513 observations. In conclusion, the findings of the study revealed that the ratio of assets turnover, long-term debt-to-total assets ratio, earnings per share, return on assets, inventory-to-total current assets ratio, total current assets-to-total assets ratio, and total assets significantly affect the market stock price of Jordanian industrial companies, while the equity-to-total assets ratio and working capital ratio have no significant effect. Consequently, the study established that the shift in the market stock prices of Jordanian industrial companies is governed by financial indicators at a relatively high level.

Nguyen and Pham (2022) empirically tested the relationship between six variables, including earnings per share, liquidity, firm size, net asset value per share, gross domestic product, and returns on assets, on the stock market returns of 359 companies listed on the Hanoi Stock Exchange by applying monthly data from 2017 to 2021. Using correlation analysis and regression analysis, the empirical results of the study showed that there are some factors that directly affect the market returns of listed stocks, including earnings per share (EPS), net asset value per share (NAVPS), and return on assets (ROA). Besides, the result could not explain the effect of liquidity, size, and gross domestic product on stock market returns.

Ogiemudia et al. (2022) examined the link between market risk and equity return in Nigeria between 1980 and 2019. They employed the vector error correction model (VECM) to determine the short run dynamics and long run effect of market risk factors on stock returns. The findings revealed that a dynamic relationship exists between market risk factors and stock returns in Nigeria. Also, exchange rate risk and oil price risk have a significant influence on stock returns, while inflation, interest rate risk, and political instability risk have a non-significant impact. Finally, a unidirectional relationship was detected between the interest rate, oil price, political instability, and stock return. The study concluded that market risk factors such as exchange rate, oil price, interest rate, and political instability risks are major determinants of stock returns in Nigeria. It is recommended that rational investors seeking maximum returns minimise market risk factors by diversifying their portfolios and study the risk behaviour and level in the market before making investment decisions.

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The reviewed empirical literature show that stock price determinants vary from one clime to another depending on the characteristics of the clime in question. The review cut across different countries stock markets and their stock price determinants. Though various approaches were adopted by different authors, it was discovered that there was no uniformity in findings as to the determinants of stock prices in these different places. This goes to confirm an earlier assertion by Oseni (nd) that stock price determinants are varied and inexhaustible. The implication of this is that, irrespective of the degree of study conducted with respect to stock price determinants, there would still exist discrepancies in findings, perhaps due to where the study is carried out and the micro and macro-environmental characteristics associated with that location. Be that as it may, the continuous search for stock pricing determinants is not foreclosed. Thus, the greater the discrepancies in findings, the more intriguing it becomes for investors to be thorough in their information search mechanisms to establish what really appeals to them while searching for where to invest their resources. Of course, what interests one investor may not interest another. Furthermore, most of the studies reviewed, if not all, were particular about one form of industry or another. However, the present study did not have a particular industry in mind. Rather, the investigation was based on fundamental macroeconomic variables identified in the literature as determinants of stock pricing.

3.0 Methodology

The method adopted for this study is an ex post facto research design that makes use of secondary data obtained for the variables of the study. The study used time series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin for the period 1981–2022. The variables of interest were market capitalization, which proxied stock pricing, and macroeconomic variables, namely, nominal gross domestic product, exchange rate, inflation, and interest rate.

Model specification

The study sought to investigate the determinants of stock pricing in the Nigeran stock market. Specifically, the study investigated the macroeconomic determinants of stock pricing in the stock market. Following this objective and in line with existing literature, the dependent variable is stock pricing, while the independent variables are exchange rate, inflation, and national income.

From the foregoing, it can be modelled that;

$$\text{MCAPt} = f(\text{Excr}, \text{Intr}, \text{NGDP}) \quad (1)$$

Where;

MCAPt = stock pricing proxied by market capitalization

Excr = exchange rate

Inf = inflation

NGDP = nominal GDP

Amending equation (1) for econometric estimation, we have;

$$\text{MCAPt} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{Excr} + \beta_2 \text{Intr} + \beta_3 \text{NGDP} + \epsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where;

α_0 = intercept

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = parametres

ϵ_t = error term.

Data source and estimation technique

The data for all the variables in the study were obtained from the CBN statistical bulletin, 2022 edition. The data were analysed using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) estimation technique in a simple multiple regression model.

4.0 Results and Findings

The results of findings based on the objective of the study is presented below.

Dependent Variable: LOG(MCAPt)

Variables	Coefficients	Std. error	t- stats.	Prob.
C	-4.782576	0.220607	-21.67921	-0.0000
INTR	-0.033972	0.008393	-4.047487	0.0002
EXCR	-0.000566	0.000623	-0.908457	0.3694
LOG(NGDP)	1.337320	0.030414	43.97116	0.0000
R2	0.995	Adj R2	0.994	Dw = 1.97

Source: Authors' computation

Macroeconomic determinants of stock pricing are presented in the table above. From the result, it is found that interest rate and nominal GDP have a statistically significant impact on stock pricing, while exchange rate does not. This finding supports Keynes liquidity preference theory, which states that speculative motives for holding money are a function of income and interest rate. Furthermore, variation in stock prices can be a function of an increase or decrease in demand and supply. The implication of this finding is that, if there is a reduction in interest rates, investors may tend to invest more in stocks, and the increasing demand for stocks may invariably bring about either an upward or downward shift in stock prices. This finding no doubt supports the findings of Rjoub et al. (2017) and Alam, Mihar, and Karim (2016) that interest rates are significantly related to stock prices. Nonetheless, the finding contradicts Machmuddah et al.'s (2020) finding that interest rates have no effect on stock prices.

The result further demonstrates that income has a positive and significant effect on stock pricing. The finding goes further to support the assertion that an increase in income can trigger an increase in demand for stocks, at least for speculative reasons for holders of idle funds. It does go to show that, like other commodities, stock prices can be influenced by the interaction of forces of demand and supply and that income is a contributing factor in determining how much of a commodity is bought at a given price. Furthermore, this finding corroborates the finding of Gunu and Idris (2009), Mehr -un - Nisa and Nishat (2012), and Alam, Mihar, and Karim (2016) that GDP significantly influences stock prices. Nonetheless, the finding contradicts Nguyen and Pham's (2022) finding that GDP does not significantly influence stock prices.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations.

Stock pricing in Nigeria embodies a complex interplay of both micro and macroeconomic factors. It cannot be said with finality the main determinant of stock pricing in Nigeria. What is certain, however, is that stock prices, like every other commodity, adjust to the interplay of forces of demand and supply in the economy. While there are alignments among some studies on the micro and macro factors affecting stock prices, this study established that, based on the unique characteristics of the Nigerian market, interest rate and income exert significant influence on stock pricing dynamics in Nigeria.

In view of the findings, enhancing transparency and corporate governance practices can bolster investor confidence and stabilize stock prices. Furthermore, policymakers should focus on maintaining macroeconomic stability, fostering a

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conducive investment climate, and improving market regulations to mitigate volatility and enhance market efficiency.

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